

PRACTICAL CLASSES ON THEORETICAL MECHANICS ARE ORGANIZED IN A VISUALLY APPEALING MANNER

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Abstract. The domino method, one of the interactive methods of teaching theoretical mechanics, is discussed in this article. The method is then applied to a specific scientific subject.

Keywords: Domino, theoretical mechanics, statics, arbitrarily spaced system of forces, initial vector, initial momentum, modulus, direction, projections, Lemma, main theorem, constituent.

The increasing demand for education all through the entire globe necessitates that higher education faculty structure the subjects they teach in a more attractive, pedagogically, and informationally demanding manner. In this instance, they should use interactive learning. Interactive learning is based on a mutual movement of students along the route of absorption of information, skills, capacities, and specific moral traits.

Currently, educational scientists are conducting various studies on teaching theoretical mechanics using new pedagogical tools. The organization of lecture sessions in support of an interactive Venn diagram is shown in works [3,6,8,11,11,16,16,19,20,28,40]. Practical solutions are given in works [2,10,25,27,39] to increase the visibility in lessons using the cluster method. The research [4,5,13,18,31,31,32,33,33,34,37] mentions methods for increasing student participation in the classroom. [1,9,14,30,35] offer an unusual approach to producing ecologically beneficial electricity utilizing wind power.

It is about the approach, which is one of the interactive ways that provides great efficiency in educational practice.

The "domino" approach is a way to activate pupils, encourage independent thinking, express their thoughts to others, and advocate for their point of view. This approach can be used to assess the comprehension of learners after passing a chapter of a subject, to repeat a topic covered in class, or to expressly assess students' knowledge.

Conditions for applying the approach to a subject:

- **Using digital cards, a group of students is separated into subgroups.**
- **Students are exposed to the Domino Method Application Procedure.**
- **Students are instructed that the method's major purpose is to determine which group will accomplish the work fast and accurately.**
- **Dominoes are divided to subgroups, and a completion time restriction is imposed.**
- **The groups must gather the dominoes within the time limit.**
- **Address errors once the operation has been done.**
- **It is evaluated based on the level of work completion by group participants.**
- **The dominoes approach has the following advantages: - the option to repeat the whole passed topic;**

Pros of the dominoes method:

- availability of an opportunity to repeat the whole passed topic;

- consolidation of group work skills of each group member in the process of working in small groups;
- achievement of students' involvement;
- development of students' ability to listen to each other.
- formation of teamwork skills.

Disadvantages of the domino method:

- the time required to apply the method;
- -high emotionality of pupils in the process of work;
- - dominoes can be closed with wrong answers.

Structure of the Domino method

Consider using the Domino technique to the topic "system of forces arbitrarily located in space" of the statics portion of theoretical mechanics. When creating a dominion, we first create a table of cards containing a query and

associated answers. The answer to the first question is replaced with the answer to the last question. We switch the questions in the remaining cells from one to the ones listed above. That is, the answer to Question 2 rather than the answer to Question 1, the answer to Question 3 rather than the answer to Question 2, the answer to Question 4 rather than the answer to Question 3, and so on. As previously stated, the answer to the last question gets swapped with the answer to question 1. Then we cut out each square, mix it up, and ask the children to arrange them in a logical sequence, completing the domino. Students in the group are separated into small groups. It is critical to focus on the equitable distribution of pupils' skills. The teacher invites small groups to construct dominoes with the same or similar number of squares. The teacher suggests that students work on the following dominoes to reinforce the idea after the topic of the system of forces placed in space. For the sake of simplicity, we reduced the number of cells in this case.

Puanso's Lemma	A system of forces arbitrarily located in space alternates with a prime moment equal to the geometric sum of the prime vector and the added pair of moments to the geometric sum of the powers given when brought to the center of some O
Head vector	As a result of moving a given force parallel to itself, a force equal to the given force and an added couple of forces are formed at the point of displacement
Head moment	$\vec{R} = \sum \vec{F}_k$
Projections of the main vector on coordinate axes	$\vec{M}_0 = \sum \vec{m}_0(\vec{F}_k)$

Head vector module	$R_x = \sum F_{kx} , R_y = \sum F_{ky} , R_z = \sum F_{kz}$
Head vector direction	$R = \sqrt{(\sum F_{kx})^2 + (\sum F_{ky})^2 + (\sum F_{kz})^2}$
Projections of the head moment on the coordinate axes	$\cos\alpha = \frac{R_x}{R} , \cos\beta = \frac{R_y}{R} , \cos\gamma = \frac{R_z}{R}$
Head torque module	$M_x = \sum m_x(\vec{F}_k) , M_y = \sum m_y(\vec{F}_k), M_z = \sum m_z(\vec{F}_k)$
Head torque direction	$M_0 = \sqrt{(\sum m_x(\vec{F}_k))^2 + (\sum m_y(\vec{F}_k))^2 + (\sum m_z(\vec{F}_k))^2}$
Basic theory of statics	$\cos\alpha = \frac{M_x}{M} , \cos\beta = \frac{M_y}{M} , \cos\gamma = \frac{M_z}{M}$

The following new table will be constructed if we deal with each cell in the given table in the sequence described above. Each row of this table is cut out and delivered at random to pupils. They confer as a group and arrange the domino pieces to make a domino. The results are analyzed and evaluated by the teacher.

Head torque module	$M_x = \sum m_x(\vec{F}_k) , M_y = \sum m_y(\vec{F}_k), M_z = \sum m_z(\vec{F}_k)$
Head vector	When a given force is moved parallel to itself, a force equal to the provided force plus a pair of additional

	forces are created at the site of displacement.
Basic theory of statics	$\cos\alpha = \frac{M_x}{M}$, $\cos\beta = \frac{M_y}{M}$, $\cos\gamma = \frac{M_z}{M}$
Projections of the head vector on the coordinate axes	$\vec{M}_0 = \sum \vec{m}_0(\vec{F}_k)$
Head vector module	$R_x = \sum F_{kx}$, $R_y = \sum F_{ky}$, $R_z = \sum F_{kz}$
Projections of the head moment on the coordinate axes	$\cos\alpha = \frac{R_x}{R}$, $\cos\beta = \frac{R_y}{R}$, $\cos\gamma = \frac{R_z}{R}$
Head vector direction	$R = \sqrt{(\sum F_{kx})^2 + (\sum F_{ky})^2 + (\sum F_{kz})^2}$
Poinsot's lemma	When a system of forces is brought to an arbitrarily situated center O, the principal vector equals the geometric sum of the provided forces, and the principal moment equals the geometric sum of the additional pairs of moments.
Head torque direction	$M_0 = \sqrt{(\sum m_x(\vec{F}_k))^2 + (\sum m_y(\vec{F}_k))^2 + (\sum m_z(\vec{F}_k))^2}$
Bosh moment	$\vec{R} = \sum \vec{F}_k$

As a result of applying the domino method to the educational process during the teaching period, students' interest in the subject they are studying increases,

the ability to work as a team in small groups is formed, the skills to respect the opinion of equals, to properly defend one's opinion are formed, in the field of science is able to find a logical sequence between concepts, key words and phrases, formulas.

We can conclude from the above that the employment of the domino technique, one of the interactive approaches, to boost the activity of students in theoretical mechanics practical training sessions has a positive effect. Students gain cooperation skills, the capacity to defend their own perspective, and the ability to compete in learning as a result of employing this strategy. All of this contributes to a qualitative growth in pupils' understanding.

References:

1. Gafurovich, D. U., & Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). The use of non-conventional power sources is a requirement of the period. *Academicia Globe*, 2(07), 121-126.
2. Mahmudov, Z. S., Daminov, J. A., & Rahimov, A. M. (2018). The Use Of Cluster Method In Lectures On Theoretical Mechanics. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol*, 27, 145-147.
3. Mahmudov, Z. (2021). Application Of Venn Diagrams In Lectures On Theoretical Mechanics. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol*, 24, 219-222.
4. Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). A Way To Increase Students Activity In The Organization Of Lectures. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol*, 25, 90-92.
5. Махмудов, З. С., & Дехканов, У. Г. (2021). Повышение благосостояния народа-основная цель государства. *Электронный инновационный вестник*, (3), 12-14.
6. Mahmudov, Z. S., & Najmiddinov, I. B. Improving the quality of education on the basis of demonstrations in lectures. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol*, 27, 80-85.
7. Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). A Method of Assessing Students' Knowledge in Practical Classes. *Design Engineering*, 9573-9578.

8. Sotivoldievich, Z. M., & Rakhimdjanovich, K. V. (2021, December). Demonstration in improving the quality of education. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 304-308).
9. Тиллабаев, Ё. К., Махмудов, З. С., Нажмиддинов, И. Б., & Азамов, Қ. С. (2017). ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ МАТНСАД ПРИ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИИ ПЕРЕХОДНЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ. *Научное знание современности*, (6), 122-125.
10. Sotivoldievich, Z. M., & Rakhimdjanovich, K. V. (2021). The Problem Of Organizing Exhibitions Of Theoretical Mechanics Lessons. *Design Engineering*, 9569-9572.
11. Махмудов, З. С. (2021). Применение диаграммы Венна на занятиях. *Электронный инновационный вестник*, (1), 4-5.
12. Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). About a new way of assessing students' knowledge in lectures. *International Engineering Journal for Research & Development*, 6(5).
13. Махмудов, З. С., Тиллабоев, Ё. К., Рахимов, А. М., & Нажмиддинов, И. Б. (2017). Ҳозирги кун ёшлари олдига қўйиладиган вазифалар хусусида. *Научное знание современности*, (6), 11-14.
14. Махмудов, З. (2016). Возможности теории графа в электрических системах. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (7 (13)), 310-315.
15. Abduvalievich, D. J., Sotivoldievich, M. Z., Mutalovich, R. A., & Biloldinovich, N. I. (2022). ON THE ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE IN THE LESSONS OF STRUCTURAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11, 14-20.
16. Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2022). The use of venn diagrams in independent study of theoretical mechanics. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11, 192-197.
17. Sotivoldievich, Z. M., & Rakhimdjanovich, K. V. (2021). About the Method of Assessing Students' Knowledge. *Design Engineering*, 9579-9585.
18. Махмудов, З. С., Даминов, Ж. А., Рахимов, А. М., & Азамов, Қ. С. (2017). Курувчи-муҳандисларга назарий механика фанини ўқитишда фанлараро узвийликни таъминлаш. *Научное знание современности*, (8), 20-22.

- 19.Махмудов, З. С., Даминов, Ж. А., & Юлдашев, Ф. Ш. (2022). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ДИАГРАММЫ ВЕННА НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *НАУЧНЫЙ ЭЛЕКТРОННЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ «МАТРИЦА НАУЧНОГО ПОЗНАНИЯ*, 44.
- 20.Махмудов, З. С., & Даминов, Ж. А. (2022). НАЗАРИЙ МЕХАНИКА ФАНИ ДАРСЛАРИНИ КЎРГАЗМАЛИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ МАСАЛАСИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 709-715.
- 21.Махмудов, З. С., & Аъзамов, К. С. (2022). О НОВОМ СПОСОБЕ ОЦЕНКИ ЗНАНИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 850-854.
- 22.Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2022). AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO ASSESS STUDENT KNOWLEDGE. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 756-761.
- 23.Mahmudov, Z., Najmiddinov, I., & Yuldasheva, B. (2022). USING THE CONFUSED LOGICAL CHAIN METHOD IN ASSESSING STUDENT KNOWLEDGE. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 1(7), 4-12.
- 24.Sotivoldievich, M. Z. Mutalovich RA ABOUT A WAY TO EVALUATE STUDENTS'INDEPENDENT LEARNING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN*, 2277-3630.
- 25.Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Azamov, K. S. (2023). USING THE CLUSTER METHOD FOR CONDUCTING LECTURES ON THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 17(02), 1-5.
- 26.Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Mutalovich, R. A. (2023). ABOUT A METHOD OF EVALUATING STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE IN THEORETICAL MECHANICS LECTURES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 17(02), 6-12.
- 27.Махмудов, З. С., & Рахимов, А. М. (2023). Применение метода кластер для проведения лекционных и практических занятий. *IQRO*, 2(2), 239-242.
- 28.Махмудов, З. С., & Аъзамов, К. С. (2023). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ДИАГРАММЫ ВЕННА НА ЛЕКЦИОННЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *IQRO*, 2(2), 248-251.

29. Mahmudov, Z. S. (2022). Isaboev Sh. M., Abdujabborov AA, Rakhmatillaev YN Use of Modern Methods of Assessing Students' Knowledge. *Undishapur Journal of Microbiology*, 15(1), 3280-3286.
30. Алиназаров, А. Х., Выровой, В., & Махмудов, З. (2005). Особенности гетерогенности среды на распределение усадочных деформаций в золоцементных вяжущих материалах. *Проблемы механики*, (4), 7.
31. Mahmudov, Z. S., & Najmiddinov, I. B. (2023). MILLIY AN'ANALARGA ASOSLANGAN "USTOZ-SHOGIRD" TIZIMIDAN FOYDALANISH. *IQRO*, 2(2), 330-334.
32. Mahmudov, Z. S., Tillaboev, Y. K., & MA'RUZA, M. U. M. H. USULIDAN FOYDALANISH//IQRO JURNALI.–2023. T, 2, 604-608.
33. Махмудов, З. С., & Тиллабоев, Ё. К. (2016). Роль учебно-методического комплекса в повышении качества знаний студентов-энергетиков. *Online electric*, 6, 18.
34. Mahmudov, Z., & Ahmadaliev, K. M. (2009). On a way to increase the activity of students in the organization of lectures on theoretical mechanics. In *Proceedings of the International Scientific and Technical Conference "Modern Problems of Mechanics"*, Tashkent (Vol. 2, pp. 381-383).
35. Юлдашев, Ш. С., Махмудов, З. С., & Жумабоева, Ш. Р. (2005). Решение несимметричной задачи о распространении вибрации, возникающей при движении поездов по одному пути двухпутного тоннеля метрополитена как суперпозиции симметричной и кососимметричной задачи. *Проблемы механики*, (4), 37-40.
36. Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Mutalovich, R. A. (2022). ABOUT A WAY TO EVALUATE STUDENTS'INDEPENDENT LEARNING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11, 165-170.
37. Махмудов, З. С. (2023). НАЗАРИЙ МЕХАНИКА ФАНИ КИНЕМАТИКА БЎЛИМИ МАВЗУЛАРИНИ ЎЎҚИТИШДА ИННОВАЦИОН ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР.
38. Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Mutalovich, R. A. (2023). ABOUT A METHOD OF EVALUATING STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE IN THEORETICAL MECHANICS LECTURES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 17(02), 6-12.
39. Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Azamov, K. S. (2023). USING THE CLUSTER METHOD FOR CONDUCTING LECTURES ON THEORETICAL

MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 *Impact Factor: 6.876, 17(02), 1-5.*

40. Махмудов, З. С., & Даминов, Ж. А. (2023). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ЛЕКЦИОННЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (4-2 (107)), 650-654.
41. Tillaboev Y., Daminov J. A., Najmiddinov I. The Effect of the Number of Rotor Plates on the Vertical Axis on the Value of the Moment of Inertia// *Design Engineering*, 2021, ISSUE 09. Pages:5504-5509.
- 42.2. Daminov J.A., Tillaboev Y., Agzamov K.S., Isaboev S.M., Abdujabborov A.A. The Mechanism of Experimental Determination of the Angular Velocity of the Working Shaft of the Wind Unit// *Design Engineering*, 2021, том 9. Pages:11814 – 11821.
- 43.3. Тиллабоев Е.К., Дадамирзаев М.Г., Абдулхафизов Б.Х. (2015). [Об одном из методов решения уравнения Навье-Стокса](#) // Молодой ученый. Том 86, № 6, стр 7-12.
- 44.4. Тиллабоев Е.К., Хакимов Р.М., Холмирзаев И.А. (2015). [Организация приближённого решения уравнений состояния электрической цепи в MathCAD](#)// Молодой ученый. Том 89, № 9, стр 44-48.
- 45.5. Тиллабоев Е.К., Холмирзаев И.А. [Определение базисных контуров с помощью графа в электрических системах](#)// Теория и практика современной науки. 2016, № 7(13), стр. 315-318.
- 46.7. Тиллабоев Ё.К.. [О возможности mathcad при решения контурных уравнений электрической цепи](#)// Теория и практика современной науки. 2016, № 6-2 (12), стр 219-224.
- 47.8. Тиллабоев Е.К. Последовательности точек в m-мерном Евклидовом пространстве // *Science and Education, scientific journal*, 3:2 (2022), с.28-37.
- 48.10. Тиллабоев Е.К. О преподавании непрерывности функции многих переменных с помощью интерактивных методов // *Science and Education, scientific journal*, 3:3 (2022), с.1053-1062.
- 49.11. Dekhkonov Ulugbek, Tillaboev Yodgor, Orishov Utkirbek. [Determining the Optimal Angular Velocity of a Vertical Axis Rotor Wind Unit](#). *Jundishapur Journal of Microbiology* 15 (No.1), 3298-3302.

